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D7.3 User Forum and Organisation structure and strategy

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Abstract

The IPERION HS (IPHS) User Forum represents a supportive learning and engagement environment called *Heritage Science Academy*. The HS Academy (#HSAcademy) is an online environment designed to support a global community of users and potential users of IPHS facilities, through online seminars and training videos, as well as through social media. The aim of the HS Academy is to promote the IPHS facilities and excellent science carried out through TransNational Access projects and joint research activities, and also to engage the wider heritage science community in current issues related to heritage science policy and the wider societal issues that impact on the development of heritage science, from climate to social change. The HS Academy promotes interdisciplinarity through a holistic engagement with topics across STEM and SSH disciplines.

The HS Academy webinar series has run monthly since April 2021 and plans are currently in place to develop a programme of webinars for 2022. It is also planned for an edition of webinars to be made available that is aimed at a more junior audience, and delivered by early stage researchers – with the aim to support and engage researchers at the start of their interdisciplinary heritage science careers. All of these activities have high online visibility, both through the IPHS website and through related social media, and a truly global engagement is visible. An HS Academy anchor has been established on the professional social networking platform LinkedIn, with the aim to develop it more strongly in the future. In addition, plans are in place to survey professional organisations that are currently available to heritage scientists at national levels with the goal to analyse the potential and the need to offer more structured support in the future.

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Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Meaning
HS	Heritage Science
TNA	TransNational Access
IPHS	IPERION Heritage Science
E-RIHS	European Research Infrastructure for Heritage Science
ESR	Early Stage Researcher

Introduction

The User Forum of IPHS has at the outset been conceptualised as more than a space – virtual or physical – made available to users of IPHS to discuss research. While this is without doubt essential, the IPHS proposal stressed a need to develop not just physical meetings, but also to analyse the potential gaps that need to be filled with new training and engagement activities beyond traditional conferences.

With the onset of the pandemic, it became even more obvious that an online activity should replace physical meetings, not just to remove the need to travel, but also to enable communities to engage globally – which also supports the vision of IPHS catering to a global community of users. The idea to develop IPHS webinars proved to be extremely popular with excellent global attendance.

The webinars were quickly recognised as a source of valuable training content that needs to be captured and made available after the events themselves. This led to the initiative to develop an offer of training materials and events aimed at the widest community of heritage scientists – the HS Academy.

HS Academy

The HS Academy represents a programme of activities that jointly support training and engagement of a global community heritage scientists:

1. HS Academy webinar series
2. HS Academy Junior webinar series
3. HS Academy training videos
4. HS Academy LinkedIn platform
5. HS Academy conference
6. HS Academy direct User engagement

The above activities represent the core of the User Forum strategy of IPHS.

1. HS Academy webinar series

The webinar series (<http://www.iperionhs.eu/webinar-series/#>) is a key source of state-of-the-art information on heritage science research, facilities, policy and impact. It contributes to the development of a vibrant heritage science community, and is intended for anyone involved in interdisciplinary heritage research.

The webinar series programme is developed by the Editorial Committee consisting of:

1. Marta Castillejo
2. Hilde De Clercq
3. Victor Etgens
4. Adam Gibson
5. Alison Heritage
6. Francois Mirambet
7. Costanza Miliani
8. Luca Pezzati
9. Jana Striova
10. Matija Strlic

The plan for the 2021 series was to showcase IPHS as well as its three platforms: ARCHLAB, MOLAB and FIXLAB. In addition, four webinars were suggested to specifically focus on the new user communities that are being developed elsewhere in WP7: (i) built environment; (ii) social science and humanities; (iii) palaeontology and palaeoanthropology; (iv) archaeology. The following webinars have so far been organised:

1. 21.04.2021, Webinar #1: What is IPERION HS - An introduction into heritage science and the structure, the offer and the facilities of IPERION HS. Speakers: Matija Strlič and Jana Striova (227 participants from 34 countries)
2. 04.05.2021, Webinar #2: FIXLAB - Ivory research, followed by hints and tips on FIXLAB access. Speakers: Ina Reiche and Rémi Petitcol (147 participants from 29 countries)
3. 01.06.2021, Webinar #3: MOLAB - Islamic manuscripts, followed by hints and tips on MOLAB access. Speakers: Kristine Rose-Beers and David Buti (177 participants from 34 countries)
4. 06.07.2021, Webinar #4: ARCHLAB - Ghent Altarpiece, followed by hints and tips on ARCHLAB Access. Speakers: Astrid Harth and María Martín Gil (129 participants from 40 countries)
5. 14.09.2021, Webinar #5: Built Heritage Research Services. Moderated by Ralf Killian (176 participants from 45 countries)

The following webinars are still planned for 2021:

6. 12.10.2021, Webinar #6: Arts and Humanities Research Services. Moderated by JoAnn Cassar
7. 09.11.2021, Webinar #7: Palaeontology Research Services. Moderated by Martina Martínez de Pinillos
8. 07.12.2021, Webinar #8: Archaeology Research Services. Moderated by Gill Campbell

Organisation and promotion are developed and carried out in collaboration with IPERION HS Work Package 8 (Central support activities). Typically, this involves planning, establishment of speaker contacts, confirmation and briefing, but also a teaser video production, social media engagement, ZOOM platform setup and technical support, as well as post-event audience engagement and feedback collection. A specific hashtag has been created and associated with these activities (#HSAcademy).

The feedback typically consists of a satisfaction questionnaire as well as disciplinary engagement analysis. Approximately 2/3 of respondents (total number 51) were from the target field, meaning that webinar promotion was excellent, and the overall satisfaction was very good, with some room for improvement. This specific webinar outreached to 176 participants located in 45 countries (Fig. 1).

In terms of suggestions offered by the surveyed respondents, these normally provide a range of useful suggestions for technical topics to be covered in the future, but also:

- Subjects related to policy, management, interdisciplinarity
- Subjects of particular interest to early-stage researchers (ESR)

We will, therefore, focus on the latter two aspects in the future. Currently, the programme of webinars for 2022 is in development, with the aim to open the webinar programme for topics of a broader interest to the HS community, and a proposal is being elaborated to prepare a webinar series of particular interest to doctoral and post-doctoral researchers and practitioners.

Fig. 1: Disciplinary engagement analysis following Webinar #5 on built environment research facilities (above left) and satisfaction rating (1-lowest; 10-highest satisfaction) (above right) and the geographical outreach (bottom).

2. HS Academy Junior

The aim of attracting a younger audience, and potentially a new group of users, is to enable the next generation of heritage science researchers, i.e. PhD students and early postdocs, to self-organise (including programme development, promotion, moderation etc.) a series of webinars on topics of their selection, but focussing on science content.

A group of enthusiastic ESRs will be identified (including from Latin American countries to reinforce synergies with RESINFRA), in order to develop the activity, enabled by Task 7.2.

We will ensure that the webinar series do not clash in terms of content, and that they are separately advertised. This will also enable the involved ESRs to develop soft skills and generally ensure that our User Group has a sound basis in the young generation.

The #HSAcademy Junior webinar series will form a Committee to develop a proposal for the webinar series, to be approved by the Editorial Board for HS webinars (see above), and for the Committee to work with WP8 to establish a workflow of promotion (relying heavily on LinkedIn) such that the Central Office is not burdened with extra work.

3. HS Academy training videos

The training material is available as part of the HS Academy as:

- YouTube collection: <https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCuN9HLbVXlejT0xCjiYjHyw/videos>
- HS Academy website: <http://www.iperionhs.eu/hs-academy-resources/>

Fig. 2: HS Academy Webinar website – all webinars are announced as a teaser video, on this website, and video recordings are available post-event.

The webinar recordings are video-edited at ZVKDS/UL and uploaded to the E-RIHS YouTube video channel:

- Webinar 1: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Lv_a5FQwOuU, 235 views
- Webinar 2: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=iF2UYrVu-QA>, 146 views
- Webinar 3: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=cn4e4hxn5mc>, 111 views
- Webinar 4: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=0j2NHmXj2oA>, 47 views
- Webinar 5: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=FCW1XyIPaj0>, 37 views

In addition to the training material produced on the basis of the webinar activity, a stand-alone training video was produced on the topic of Collaborative Research Training (Fig. 3).

Fig. 3: The Collaborative research training video start frame.

The video, produced in collaboration between the E-RIHS Preparatory Phase and IPHS projects discussed collaborative research in heritage science - research carried out in collaboration between research-intensive organisations, such as academia or research institutes, and practice-led organisations, such as heritage organisations and other public bodies, policy making organisations or the general public. We ask questions, such as:

- What are the hindrances and how do we overcome them?
- How do we design a collaborative proposal that has the optimal options to succeed?
- How do we take personal motivations and institutional strategies into account?

A few foremost experts in the field of heritage science research guide the learners through the process. This training video could be suitable for anyone embarking on the development of a collaborative research project, or those wishing to improve the management of complex interdisciplinary collaborative consortia. It may also be useful for funders as they design or monitor collaborative research projects.

The following collaborated in the production of this video:

- Nancy Bell
- Cecilia Bembibre
- Loic Bertrand
- Costanza Miliani
- Polonca Ropret
- Matija Strlic.

The learning contents are largely based on the outcomes of the research project "Mind the Gap", funded by the Science and Heritage Programme of the UK Arts and Humanities Research Council.

4. HS Academy LinkedIn platform

The LinkedIn platform "Heritage Science Online Forum", supported by HS Academy, represents a growing community of professionals and currently has 577 followers. For comparison: IPHS Twitter has 785 followers, so the two platforms are doing similarly well in terms of promotion and engagement.

Fig. 4: IPERION HS Academy Online Forum on LinkedIn represents the online User Forum as defined in Task 7.2.

The LinkedIn Online Forum will be developed further, exploring links with the LinkedIn interest groups, where further interest in IPERION HS services could be developed, such as:

- Collections Preservation and Care (12,915 members)
- Collections Management in Heritage (13,038 members)
- Archaeology & Archeology (16.1K members)
- Medieval and Renaissance Art, Antiques, Architecture, Archaeology and History (17.2K members)
- The Institute of Historic Building Conservation (6.7K members)
- Heritage Conservation/Historic Preservation of the Built Environment Network (9.6K members)

In addition, the LinkedIn forum could be used to offer advice to potential applicants for TNA services, however, in order for this to become a successful way of engagement with users, LAB coordinators and facility coordinators would need to subscribe to the forum as well.

5. HS Academy conference

In collaboration with WP8, and following a batch of successful access projects, we plan to organise a conference-style event with the aim to showcase IPERION HS research excellence. Such fora have been successfully organised in the previous integrating IPERION Cultural Heritage project and pandemic permitting, we should continue with this best practice.

6. HS Academy direct engagement

As per Task 7.2 description, an important activity to ensure cohesion of the IPHS (and future E-RIHS) user community is to develop an understanding of the need to self-organise.

It is fair to say that heritage scientists in some countries already have excellent representation (e.g. the Heritage Science Group of the Institute for Conservation UK), whereas in other countries, there is no opportunity to organise, exchange experience and best practice, or to influence policy development.

We plan to carry out interviews and questionnaires for both (i) users who we see could be potential users of IPHS/E-RIHS facilities, and (ii) organisations that may or may not represent such users. Although it is unlikely that a single organisation could ever represent the multitude of interests of our users, a loose association could provide structured grassroots feedback to the practical running

of the infrastructure. Through online meetings (webinars), by engaging a new generation of users (webinar junior programme), LinkedIn activities and conferences, as well as training modules, we will already have a full range of activities that are normally offered by a professional organisation. Thus, it could be envisaged, as is the case of other large infrastructures, for a body to develop that has its own self-governed structure and provides the infrastructure with aggregated views of its members. This is essential in order to provide a framework for engagement on the personal/professional level, as currently, no such organisation exists, EU-wide or internationally. Should the need for such an organisation become apparent through the questionnaires and interviews, the legacy of this activity could stretch significantly beyond the lifetime of the project.